

Biosimulation of cyst growth effect on the distribution of stresses and strains within the bone, an answer to the old question of why we have cystic wall corticalization?

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Abstract

Tumors have many stages and grades. Stages depend upon many factors, such as size. Tumors pass through many steps to reach enormous sizes in many instances. When reaching large sizes, the distribution of the strains and stresses within the skeletal environment will be changed. These changes had many biomechanical rules. We had introduced a model for capturing a significant change in this distribution. This model needs more tuning in terms of better characterization of the features and boundary conditions.

Introduction

According to the previously proposed mechanism stand behind bone growth is associated with endochondral ossification. (1) Our model proposed 3 main elements

- Force application component
- Stiff component that provides lever action
- Deformable component that yields increasing in volume and is located at the maximum strain region

A biomechanical model of bone with a simple benign cyst is important because it shows the importance of the changes in the bone associated with cavitation in the bone and how the bone is actually enlarging. It is imperative to remember always that these models are solid, homogenous, continuous and at least the laminated structure of the bone with its unique orthotropicity had not been remodeled. (2)

Total enlargement of facial structures will be due to both soft and hard tissue components. We suggest that the enlargement of the soft tissues be preceded by the enlargement in the hard tissue component. (3)

We should always remember that the tumor had

- Mechanical arm, which is little seen by the researchers (4)
- Biological arm where all eyesight looked on (5)

Figure 1 Tumor enlargement, mechanical representation remains enigma to be solved

In almost of the pathological biochemical processes, we had excellent parametric approaches. In contrast to this in the biomechanical models we many theories based upon speculations and assumption without robust scientific evidence that stand for simple deep scrutinization.

Figure 2 Apparent enlargement of the mandible that absolutely need an explanatory biomodel. The left picture is the outer skin model of the 3D model of the skin derived from the

CT scan data for the same patient. The line over the nose representing the metallic wire associated with the mask that the patient had been wear during the CT scan data acquisition.

Mandibular hypertrophy or elongation is a pathological process entailing change in the morphology of the ramus that may extend to the body of the mandible. (6) Some conditions have no well-defined deformable region that could yield an expansion. They also need biomechanical models. In such conditions, we attribute the growth to the biological arm mostly. In this case, the change of the facial morphology is also apparent.

Figure 3 This is another case of history with mucormycosis during childhood. The subsequent changes due to the early destruction of the tissue are apparent. Both views of the patient's CT scan appearance This is apparent change due to long-standing damage in the bone.

This is another case of history with mucormycosis during childhood. We had no insight into the possible changes associated with a certain anomaly. The correlation between the causative incident and the resultant deformity is absent in the literature. In order to understand this issue, we should always remember that craniosynostosis has a consistent pattern of growth. In our paper about craniosynostosis, we had depicted very important aspects associated with premature closure of the sutures. (7) Nevertheless, we have not correlated the molecular biology and the defect in the fibroblast growth factor receptors with the resultant mechanical deformity. In contrast to the tumor, disease in the early stage of development will result in marked atrophy of the tissues. Nevertheless, both tumor and atrophy of tissue had biomechanical aspects that should be observed.

The tissue injuries, fibrosis, damaging to the growth centers will lead to opposite sequences in comparison to tumors growths by limitation of the growth in the adjacent tissues and growth centers. Our proposed theory about growth center is totally different from those suggested in the texts of orthodontics.

Figure 4 This is the 3D model of the bones of the previous patient. The disease region acts as tethering spot that prevent expansion and growth of the facial skeleton. Another view of the skeleton that show the effect of the disease on the inferior orbital margin in relation to the contralateral side

This is apparent change due to long standing damage in the bone. The bony change involves the maxilla. Nose and orbit. This is the same as what will happen in the case of clefting. It is evident what is the effect of tissue damage is on the facial skeleton.

Figure 5 The effect had been extended to involve many parts of the paranasal sinuses system.

The development of the paranasal sinuses is also affected by the osseous condition of the patient. The maxillary sinus plays an important role in midface development. (8)

Figure 6 Axial slice of a patient with ameloblastoma in the right side of the mandible. Ameloblastoma is regarded as a soft region in the mandible, and its origin has a significant effect upon the molecular messaging in the peritumor melia

Figure 7 Although good pathological evaluation of the ameloblastoma has been reached, but its mechanical aspect, including its effect upon the mandible, still needs exploring

Axial section at the tumor region. A mechanical description is highly needed.

Figure 8 Coronal view of the CT scan of the patient with ameloblastoma.

Coronal section at the tumor region. The mechanical description is highly needed.

Figure 9 The change will absolutely affect the facial appearance. Thinning of the cortical plates is associated with an increase in the volume of the medullary space.

The anatomical regions involvement should be reviewed carefully. How the tumor is growing is a story that needs to be told.

Figure 10 The relative enlargement of the ramus of the mandible is apparent from this view.

The growth of the tumor is absolutely aided by the deformation of the mandible during daily activity.

Figure 11 This patient had an aggressive form of fibrous dysplasia the necessitate surgical intervention in the early stage. Effects upon the soft tissues is resulted from the changes in the skeleton is apparent

The usage of the heavy metallic components is highly discouraged. The surgery by itself is an iatrogenic trauma that hinder the growth to great extent. Significant events had been happened to this young lady

- fibrous dysplasia abnormal growth
- tumor resection
- placement of the metallic implant and the surgical injury itself

The soft tissue growth is guided by the bone changes

Figure 12 This is another patient with a tumor involving the left side of the mandibular ramus extending to the body. Marked facial asymmetry accompanying the bony lesion.

Figure 13 These changes had rules, but we had not established the basis to understand them.

Figure 14 This is a young patient diagnosed with fibrous dysplasia of the mandible on the right side.

Figure 15 The coronal section shows clearly the enlarged mandibular ramus and the effect upon the soft tissues. The disease is also evident at the axial section.

Figure 16 At the level of the beginning of the mandibular canal. How genetic disorders affect the bone is a story that needs more speech in the next edition if Almighty God will. The tumor tissues had capability to ignite a new growth center like pattern.

We also think that the tumor had a staging in a growth that is governed by stiffness rules in a certain anatomical domain. The tumor growth rate is not uniform at all stages and also levering will be available. (9)

The weakening of some parts of the jaws provides an unparalleled mechanism of reciprocal loading. Reciprocal loading also affects the dentition also during orthodontics treatment.

We will do this simulation in the next papers if Allah wills, then it will be so.

If we have a tumor in the anterior part of the mandible it will behave differently if it was in the posterior region of the mandible or even in the maxilla if we assume the same conditions or variables.

The same tumor could assume different manifestations. According to different variables, patience and the anatomical location are considered. The tumors had biomechanical roles. Benin growth (e.g. Simple lipoma behave in soft tissues like a simple radicular cyst in bones), while biological behaviors of the malignant tumors could control the dynamic changes in the morphology or the way it affects its surroundings (e.g. Like carcinoma or in case of sarcomatous growth in the mandible with central extension without enlargement of the jaws). Growth in the previous 2 examples is also absolutely governed by global stiffness rules. At certain anatomical regions, but also biologically, the tumor had different story to be told. (10)

Surgeons who dealing with such pathological entities understand this just from dealing with fresh specimens.

To understand tumor growth, we should present an engineering model that enables us to understand the process itself or some model close or at least explore many aspects of this model. Our current model, as well as previous models could provide an entry to a better understanding of the tumor growth. Tumor growth should not be isolated from the orthodontics movement that affects the dentition. We should establish a well-correlated relationship between the results of the orthodontic movement and the change in the shape of the alveolar process.

This coordination should be parametric. Many lesions are associated with orthodontic movement of the teeth which is highly stable even after removal of the tumor, in contrast to the formal planned orthodontics movement that is done at the dental clinics, where relapse still for all cases or so, whatever the treatments is, by which it represents a nightmare for the orthodontist. The relationship of the outer surface of the alveolus to the achieved orthodontic movement should be studied well, as it gives us a clue about an important aspect of the biomechanics in orthodontics.

Delaying the tumor treatment with tomographic follow up the change in volume and morphology of the tumors for research purposes is totally unjustified. Nevertheless, animal experiments could provide unparalleled insights. Nevertheless, we could benefit from post-chemotherapy follow-up by utilizing tomographic radiographic modalities, which is already used by the oncologist to follow up tumor's size and morphology to decide which treatment protocol is followed.

Methods

We had presented these models

- shaft of a long bone, we had selected such model as it simple and its comparison across other geometrical variant is easier
- simple cyst growth
- stiffer cyst wall
- enlarged cyst walls

Tumor growth is the result from

- Its biological modulating capacity mimics the primary growth center. This is achieved via soft, turning of the bone into less stiff material. We believe that this softening is stand behind the enlargement mechanism
- Loading status of the bone. The tumor in its early stage will be a part of normally loaded bone

In case of Benign epithelial cysts in the mandible or maxilla, the cortication in the cyst walls is due to the disturbed stresses distribution. This disruption in the distribution will affect bone histology. In case of tumor growth that involve bone, we have these factors:

- biological ability of different pathological process to reshape the bone or change its structure via different paracrine and endocrine pathways
- pressure effect will add another factor
- flow of different fluids between layers of the osseous tissues should be studied well
- bone architecture changes whether over-corticalization (called in orthopedics cortical hypertrophy or osteolysis due to stress shielding or due to the action of the tumor itself should be studied well. the chronological events should be arranged

Osteolysis due to certain factors such as hydrostatic pressure that is occurring in the case of simple epithelial cysts stand behind part of the growing capability of the cyst, while the increase radiolucency in the periphery of the cyst could be explained by

- Ability of the bone to cope with these changes. The bone had the ability to remodel results in enhanced the cortication in regions needed more strength
- Increase in the osseous mass could lead to push the bone tissue strengthening capability to its ultimate limit resulting in obliteration of the medullary space and formation of a solid mass of highly calcified consistency, dentine like consistency. This is well-known by many surgeons and this could explain trabecular changes associated.
- Limited ability of these pathologies to induce bony histology changes.

In order to make a model with simple features that could be modified as well as enable us to make a direct comparison after each modification is done, we tried to simplify the current model as much as we can. The diaphysis of any bone had the least medullary component and mainly formed from highly cortical walls and very soft internal material. This is an engineering description of the long bones.

Another mechanical description where the medullary bone or irregular bone play as significant alloying mechanical effect and act as an infill material with orthotropicity that is oriented to obtain certain resistance mechanically and this is determined by the loading action that is exposed to the bone. Although this sentence could be vague for many researchers, but we think it is highly valid when we understand the bone as fiber-reinforced composite.

Which event is preceding the other event, biological event or stress disturbance event that ignite the change in the shape or size and affects the bone histology should be studied well. Biological events produced tumors will result in stress distribution disturbance and vice versa, by which

the stress disturbance in return produce change in the biology. This reciprocation would stimulate the growth process resulting in osseous metamorphism.

Reciprocation in loading is the leading event in a growth and development as we had demonstrated in our previously published papers. (11) The stresses distribution within the bone due to the loading condition of the bone itself play a very important role in shaping of the net effect of the pathologies on the bone.

The presence of intra-lesional separation that impart soap bubble appearance in plain radiographs that occurs in the osteoblastoma should be understood in the context of the tumor biomechanics as well as global stiffness and the original architecture of the bone itself. Composite structure of bone could allow four tumor growth in certain directions. (12)

In the case of soft tissue, we have what is called fascial spaces that in reality presents a potential space and infection will easily spread via them. We think that tumors grow inside of bone in the least resistance direction. There could be sparing of part of the bone in between two stiff regions there is another softer region susceptible regions the tumor could grow through. This could be explanation for the multilobulated presentation

Presence of weakening points in the bone anatomy could be regarded as a site for tumor growth and spread. There are weakening points in the bony composite structure that could be aggravated by the tumor resulting in concentration of stresses and pushing the growth in certain direction.

Figure 17 This is the model that represent the shaft of a long bone

Figure 18 The yellow dots represent unmovable region of the bone. The red arrows represent the load direction. One of the ends is fixed and the other end has force with the X direction.

Normal bone anatomy is composed from 3 parts:

- Central part by which a very soft material had been assigned
- Intermediate part which had been represented by intermediate mechanical properties between the outermost layer and the innermost layer
- Outermost layer had been assigned with a stiff material previously used in our Mohammed bodies for growth and trauma

The Central part and intermediate layers have no significant mechanical role, but certainly have important from a biological perspective both systemically and locally. Again, this is a mechanical representation of an anatomical domain.

Figure 19 In this model we had representing a simple cyst is separating the 2 middle components and reduce the mass of the outermost cortex.

Figure 20 Model of cyst with stiffer wall. It is better to modify this model to give more smooth results. An additional model of weaker walls should be represented

Figure 21 Model with enlarged cyst wall

We agree that these models are oversimplified to represent the jaws or even a long bone, but we had done it to convey our ideas and present an initial entity to the modern biomechanics via the door of state-of-art analysis, namely finite element analysis(FEA), about the possible osseous tissue response in more comprehensible engineering way and to explore hiding aspects of performance you to change in the macro features we should always remember that the bone are composite in composite material where any numerical simulation. Such structure is a very

complex to be achieved and no direct comparison could be made as in this case of bone we are representing a simple continuous homogeneous isotropic material in contrast to composite structure in reality.

Results and discussions

Figure 22 This figure represents the normal anatomy model strain energy density.

It had been agreed in the bioengineering community that this criterion of evaluation (strain energy density) is the indicator for the bone remodeling. (13) In all of the next models, we had unified the legend to make a comprehensible comparison. Unification of the legends had been done in all of the other comparisons criteria.

Figure 23 this is the enlarged of the most important region of this model

Due to the current virtual experimental boundary conditions, this pattern is anticipated to occur while in reality the result is totally different. We think that the irregularity in the distribution of the strain energy is the cause of some variation in the anatomy across different regions of a single bone.

Development of process that represent muscular attachment such as mastoid process, could be attributed due to stiffening at a region and programmed softening at another region, in another word: the base of the bony process.

Figure 24 Many irregular bones had many processes that associated with muscular action

Figure 25 Here you should put mandible of child mandibles of an adult and edentulous person to compare the different shapes between all the mandibles and its different chronological and physiological developmental Stages. Stiffness played significant role in determination over the shape of the bone

The differences in mechanical loading across different regions stand behind the overcriticalization in some regions that could be expressed via different projections and processes. These processes should be and understood in the context of certain anatomy response to loadings.

Figure 26 Different lines and tubercles is well known on the external surface of the mandible with high consistency in location in relation to the muscles and other anatomical structures these make distinct and atomic up barriers.

Figure 27 Normal anatomy forms an inner view of the bone. We think that this simple model is the representation of normal Anatomy. Each specimen should be inspected from inside and outside from different angles and views.

Figure 28 Another view of the normal bone model. Cross section of the long bones is highly affected by the function associated with that bone.

Figure 29 Model representing bone with central cyst.

The appearance and you separated region of the train energy density is highly apparent and it is suited to explain the constitution that occur in the bones around and surrounding cyst.

Figure 30 Model representing bone with central cyst

In the model with central cyst, we should do a direct comparison with other models. It is better to try to reduce color numbers to make more easily comparison between these models.

Figure 31 Another view of model representing bone with central cyst. This region should be understood clearly.

((Separation of the new region from the other regions will indicate certain amount of transitions. We should know that whether which is the first process then we can call the strains and stresses distribution or the biological aspects that affect the structure of the bone))

Figure 32 Model representing bone with central cyst and stiffer cyst's wall

In the model representing bone with central cyst and stiffer cyst's wall, we had a sharp transition from the stiffer region in the middle to the softer region on both peripherals, we have sharply delineated margin. This will not occur in reality as we have always smoother gradient of changes in case of bone pathologies

Figure 33 Model representing bone with central cyst and stiffer cyst's wall

In the model representing bone with central cyst and stiffer cyst's wall, the same previous model but with a different configuration. Many pathologies presenting with different capability to induce sclerosis or increase in the cortication, while others produce weakening of the osseous structure by partial or total osteolysis.

Figure 34 Another view of the model representing bone with central cyst and stiffer cyst's wall.

Figure 35 Model representing bone with central cyst and enlarged cyst's wall. When enlargement in the bond structure take place, it will result in different stress distribution the stiffness should understood in this context.

Figure 36 Model representing bone with central cyst and enlarged cyst's wall.

Figure 37 Another view of the model representing bone with a central cyst and enlarged cyst's wall. When a change in the properties of the segment of bone it will lead to different growth in that segment as well as the adjacent regions.

Such change will be guided by biological aspect of the anatomical region or by the pathology. It will lead to change in the bony structure. We have no idea about the any disturbance in the stiffness what a trigger a cascade of that we have not settled a model to represent it yet apart from some models one of these models is the numerical simulation of the citrus shielding and excellent simulating between radiographic clinical and numerical models

In our previously presented models, we had represented many highly valid models for different pathological processes. The current is the arrangement of the models according to the resultant displacement maximum displacement which indicate partial stiffness

- The model with the least stiffness is the model of the cyst 0.291mm
- The second model reduced stiffness is the normal bond module 0.287mm
- Expanded model is the third in the term of reduced stiffness 0.277mm
- The model with highest stiffness is the model was stiffer smalls of the cyst 0.272mm

Figure 38 Displacement of the normal model

Figure 39 Maximum displacement of the normal model 0.871mm

Figure 40 Displacement of the simple cystic model. Stiffness in you to increase mass in contrast to the cystic model.

Increased stiffness indicated by reduced total displacement. Is it due to an increased mass in contrast to simple cyst, that is characterized by a reduced mass of the model. Enlarge cystic model represent an increase stiffness you to increase mass in contrast to the cystic model

Figure 41 Maximum displacement of the cystic model 0.2913mm

Figure 42 Displacement of the model with stiffer cyst's walls

Figure 43 Maximum displacement of the model with stiffer cyst's walls 0.272 mm

Figure 44 Displacement of the model with enlarged cyst's walls

Displacement Magnitude [mm]

Max 2.8016e-01

2.5000e-01

2.2650e-01

Figure 45 Maximum displacement of the model with enlarged cyst's walls 0.280 mm

Figure 46 Strain of the normal unaltered model

Figure 47 Strain of the cystic model. Strain in the walls of the cyst is higher at the same spot in comparison to the same spot in the normal model analogue.

Figure 48 Strain of the cystic model with a stiffer cyst wall.

Figure 49 Strain of the model with enlarged cystic wall.

The bone is a laminated composite material that should be understood in this context in all discussions about any detail related to the biomechanics. Any decision about any details in the subject of biomechanics should be understood in the context of composite inside composites structure of the bone.

In reality, we suspect that the cyst walls are less in terms of stiffness due to reduced strength in terms of thickness and reduced cortication in many tumors with biological activities through different molecular pathways.

Some pathologies had the least possible effect upon the composite structure of the bone representation by the long duration until reach a size with clinical features of jaws enlargement and the accompanying cortication in the bony walls of the cyst is evident clinically or radiographically. Some could be diagnosed by chance (e.g. a dentist wants to take radiographs for impacted lower 8 and discover a big lesion)

Conclusions

We had demonstrated an important aspect of the mechanical performance of a model that represent a cyst after a considerable increase in size. This will lead to a change in the pericystic bone density due to disturbed strain and stresses

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